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Variations in Global and diffuse radiation of Patna, Varanasi and Vishakhapatnam (1985-2015)

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Abstract :

Solar energy is a favourable, inexhaustible and promising source of renewable energy. The importance of Solar energy is compounded by its location for example tropical and equatorial latitudes, where the ground surface receives ample of its energy throughout the year. A precise and comprehensive knowledge about solar radiation is crucial for harnessing and for the conversion of solar energy. There are several factors that determine variations in solar radiation which includes rotation of earth on its axis, sun's rays' angle of inclination, day length, transparency and land's configuration. This paper will assess the amount

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and variation of Global and diffuse radiation received at Patna (25°-36° N Latitudes and 85°-10°E longitudes), Varanasi (25°-18° N latitudes and 83°-01° E longitudes) and Visakhapatnam (17°-41° N latitudes and 83°-18° E longitudes) for the period of 30 years (1985-2015) and will try to analyze the correlation between the global solar radiation and hours of sunshine received at these places. The analysis of results substantiates that; there is variation in Global and Diffuse components of solar radiation in summer and winter months. During winter months when the sky remains bright and clear the percentage and contribution of diffuse solar radiations to global solar radiation is low. Hence, months of March, April, May seem more preferable for utilization of Sun's energy due to high direct radiation and low percentage of diffuse radiation for solar cookers, solar furnaces, solar concentrators and other solar devices.

Keywords : Direct radiation, Global radiation, Diffuse radiation, Sunshine hour.

1. Introduction :

Solar radiation is the energy that is emitted by the sun in the form of electromagnetic radiation. Solar radiations are becoming increasingly appreciated because of their influence on living matter and the feasibility of its application for useful purposes (Bhatia, 2014). It can be classified into Global, Diffuse and Direct radiation. Direct radiation is described as solar radiation that is travelling in a straight line from the sun down to the surface of the earth; on the other hand, presence of molecules and particles in the atmosphere scatters the emitted sun's radiation and is called Diffuse solar radiation. Direct radiation has a definite path or direction; on the contrary diffuse radiation follows an indefinite path. The sum total of direct and diffuse radiation is called Global radiation.

In the era of climate change and global warming solar energy has played a favourable, inexhaustible and promising source of renewable energy not just in the past, but its relevance has continued in present and will certainly contribute in future too. The importance of Solar energy is compounded by its location for example tropical and equatorial latitudes, where the ground surface receives ample of its energy throughout the year. As the conventional sources of energy like coal, petroleum et cetera are dwindling along with adding pollutants to the environment, there is an urgent need for the entire humanity to tap green energy. Among the other

non-conventional resources, the sun is the primary source. A precise and comprehensive knowledge about solar radiation is crucial for harnessing and for the conversion of solar energy. This paper will assess the amount and variation of Global and diffuse radiation received at Patna (25° - 36° N Latitudes and 85° - 10° E longitudes), Varanasi (25° - 18° N latitudes and 83° - 01° E longitudes) and Vishakhapatnam (17° - 41° N latitudes and 83° - 18° E longitudes) for the period of 30 years (1971-2000) and will try to analyse the correlation between the global solar radiation and hours of sunshine received at these places. The analysis of results substantiates the fact that there is variation in Global and Diffuse components of solar radiation in different months. During winter month when the sky remains bright and clear the percentage and contribution of diffuse solar radiations to global solar radiation is low. Hence, months of March, April, May seems more preferable for utilisation of Sun's energy due to high direct radiation and low percentage of diffused radiation for solar cookers, solar concentrators, solar furnaces and other solar devices.

2. Study Area :

Patna (Bihar), Varanasi (Uttar Pradesh) and Vishakhapatnam (Andhra Pradesh) are located geographically in India, they are the important cities of their respective states. The other details are as follows :

S.No	Station	LAT °N	LONG °E	Elevation (m)	Data Availability
1	Patna	25-36	85-10	51	1986-2015
2	Varanasi	25-18	83-01	90	1983-2015
3	Vishakhapatnam	17-41	83-18	7	1971-2015

Figure 1 : Location of Study Area on Map of India

3. Aims and Objective :

Paper's objective is to reflect the trends and variation of Global and Diffuse radiation of three cities of India that is Patna, Varanasi, Vishakhapatnam. And with the help of observed value to find out which are the optimum months for tapping solar energy and to ensure energy efficiency and bridge the gap of energy deficiency.

4. Data Sources :

The data of Daily Normal of Global and Diffuse radiation (1985-2015) was collected from the library of the Indian Meteorological Department, issued by the Climate Division Office of Additional Director General of Meteorology (Research), Indian Meteorological Department, Pune, 2016.

5. Methodology :

Correlation coefficients, which is used to find how strong a relationship exists between two variables, have been used in this study to prove that there exists a positive relation between sunshine hour and global radiation which determines the amount of radiation earth surface will receive. Further, the monthly variation of Global, Diffuse radiation and Sunshine hours of three different spaces on the same graph and monthly trend of the Global, Diffuse and Sunshine Hours of particular place has been represented through the use of multiple line graphs after calculating mean of the daily observed Global and Diffuse radiation and by summing the monthly observation.

6. Limitations of the Study :

The whole study is based on the analysis of secondary data sources. Since, the meteorological stations were not opened initially in Patna and Varanasi, so the data from 1971 for stations of Patna and Varanasi is not available, and hence data is collected from the year of its availability. The study has limited itself in simply representing the variations and trends of three selected stations of Patna, Varanasi and Vishakhapatnam and no further attempt has made in predicting the upcoming radiation trends by using the widely used Angstrom-Prescott method of estimating Global and diffuse solar radiation.

7. Results and Discussions :

Annual global radiation of 30 years of Patna, Varanasi and Vishakhapatnam is 6388.82 MJ/m², 6393.75 MJ/m² and 6977.35 MJ/m² respectively (Table 1.1). The highest monthly global radiation is in the months of March, April and May for all the three stations. Vishakhapatnam has relatively higher Global radiation as compared to Patna and Varanasi. Monthly variation of Global radiation is also less in Vishakhapatnam due to its latitudinal location, which receives solar energy throughout the year.

Annual Diffuse radiation of three stations are Patna 2791.24 MJ/m², Varanasi 2890.67 MJ/m² and Vishakhapatnam 2983.52 MJ/m². Diffuse radiation is high during summer months owing to the larger number of clouds due to convective heating of lands, high amount of moisture present in atmosphere, on the other hand, during winter month when the sky remains bright and clear the percentage and contribution of diffuse solar radiations to global solar radiation is low. Vishakhapatnam has comparatively higher diffuse radiation from June to December. The total mean sunshine hour duration for all the months are 6.99 for Patna, 7.79 for Varanasi and 7.2 for Vishakhapatnam.

Table 1.1 : Monthly Mean Global Radiation

Monthly Mean Global Radiation(MJ/m²)			
Months	Patna	Varanasi	Vishakhapatnam
Jan.	404.17	393.86	560.05
Feb.	494.75	491.04	596.52
Mar.	645.29	658.12	697.29
Apr.	685.16	682.52	699.93
May	704.75	708.97	704.1
Jun.	603.16	604.13	537.63
Jul.	501.11	498.29	515.1
Aug.	519.67	528.56	511.74
Sep.	496.04	494.45	537.56
Oct.	521.82	525.02	570.19
Nov.	440.31	432.02	517.33
Dec.	372.59	376.77	529.91
Annual	6388.82	6393.75	6977.35

Figure 2 : Monthly Mean Variation of Global Radiation of Patna, Varanasi and Vishakhapatnam

Table 1.2 : Monthly Mean Diffuse Radiation

Monthly Mean Diffuse Radiation(MJ/m ²)			
Months	Patna	Varanasi	Vishakhapatnam
Jan.	172.97	174.95	180.94
Feb.	176.24	173.26	180.6
Mar.	212.76	220.73	229.61
Apr.	259.22	266.42	254.56
May	314.39	316.45	302.17
Jun.	307.52	335.19	323.72
Jul.	308.44	321.39	335.54
Aug.	293.63	309.56	331.26
Sep.	244.39	254.3	279.5
Oct.	191.22	197.76	213.73
Nov.	151.4	158.96	180.57
Dec.	159.06	161.7	171.32
	2791.24	2890.67	2983.52

Figure 3 : Monthly Mean Variation of Diffuse Radiation of Patna, Varanasi and Vishakhapatnam

Table 1.3 : Monthly Mean Sunshine

Monthly Mean Sunshine (Hours)			
Months	Patna	Varanasi	Vishakhapatnam
Jan.	6.7	7.5	8.8
Feb.	8.1	8.5	9.6
Mar.	8.4	9.4	8.8
Apr.	8.8	9.8	8.8
May	8.8	9.7	8.1
Jun.	6.4	7.8	4.5
Jul.	4.2	4.6	4.2
Aug.	4.9	6.1	4.3
Sep.	5.4	6.5	5.6
Oct.	7.7	8.3	7.4
Nov.	8	8.7	7.6
Dec.	6.5	6.6	8.7
	6.99	7.79	7.2

Figure 4 : Monthly Mean Variation of Sunshine (Hours)

7.1 Variation in Global and Diffuse Radiation :

Global radiation is highest in Patna in the month of May (704.75 MJ/M^2), followed by April (685.16 MJ/m^2), March (645.29 MJ/m^2) and June (603.16 MJ/m^2). The percentage of diffuse radiation (fig. 5) is highest in the month of July 61.55% followed by August 56.50% and June 50.98% which is the month of monsoon in north India, so the possibility of scattering from the atmosphere increases. Hence these months are not good for acquiring solar energy in Patna. On the contrary, when the Global radiation is high and percentage of diffuse radiation is less as compared to other months, provides good opportunity to equip solar energy conversion example months of March, April and May.

Figure 5 : Variation in Global and Diffuse Radiation in Patna

Global radiation is highest in Varanasi in the month of May (708.97 MJ/M^2), followed by April (682.52 MJ/m^2), March (658.12 MJ/m^2) and June (604.13 MJ/m^2). There is a very slight difference in the observed Global and Diffuse radiation of Patna and Varanasi, owing to the fact that they both lie in the same latitude. The percentage of diffuse radiation (fig. 6) is highest in the month of July 61.50% followed by August 58.57% and June 55.48% which is again the month of monsoon in north India, so the possibility of scattering from the atmosphere increases due to the presence of clouds. Hence these months are not good for capturing solar energy in Varanasi. On the other hand, when the Global radiation is high and percentage of diffuse radiation is less as compared to other months, provides good opportunity to equip solar energy conversion, example months of March, April and May.

Figure 6 : Variation in Global and Diffuse Radiation in Varanasi

From the analysis of thirty-year data (1985-2015), the observation established the fact that Global radiation is highest in Vishakhapatnam in the month of May (704.1 MJ/M^2), followed by April (699.93 MJ/m^2), March (697.29 MJ/m^2) and October (570.19 MJ/m^2). The percentage of diffuse radiation (fig. 7) is highest in the month of July 65.14% followed by August 64.73% and June 60.12%. Hence these months are not good for harnessing solar energy in Vishakhapatnam. The months of March, April and May provide the period of harnessing solar energy efficiently.

In addition, percentage of diffuse radiation is high in the winter month in northern India, when compared to Vishakhapatnam, which lies in southern India,

due to relatively less fluctuating weather conditions of southern India, for example in Patna and Varanasi the percentage of diffuse radiation in the months of January and December, which are the coldest month of Northern India, moving around 40% of the total but in Vishakhapatnam the percentage is 30%.

Figure 7 : Variation in Global and Diffuse Radiation in Vishakhapatnam

7.2 Correlation between Global Radiation and Sunshine Hours :

There exists a positive correlation between Sunshine hours and Global radiation, as longer duration of Sunshine will provide more opportunity for the earth’s surface to receive solar radiation and more possibility of tapping solar energy. Correlation value is positive for all the three study areas, with Patna having a value of 0.47, Varanasi 0.57, and Vishakhapatnam 0.58. There is a slight difference in the observed correlated values of the stations. It is corroborated from the available data that there exists a positive correlation between Global solar radiation and Sunshine hours.

Figure 8 : Correlation between Sunshine Hour and Global Solar radiation (Patna)

Figure 9 : Correlation between Sunshine Hour and Global Radiation (Varanasi)

Figure 10 : Correlation between Sunshine Hour and Global Radiation (Vishakhapatnam)

8. Suggestions and Recommendations :

The results obtained after data analysis specify that the solar energy conversion and utilization has a promising and bright future in all these three places of India, especially in the months of March, April and May. The analysis of results substantiates that; there is variation in Global and Diffuse components of solar radiation in summer and winter months. During winter months when the sky remains bright and clear the percentage and contribution of diffuse solar radiations to global solar radiation is low. Hence, months of March, April, May, seems more

preferable for utilisation of Sun's energy due to high direct radiation and low percentage of diffuse radiation for solar cookers, solar concentrators, solar furnaces and other solar devices. Furthermore, the maximum energy can be produced when the sun's ray is directly perpendicular to solar panels. Also, distribution of diffuse radiation throughout the sky may be gathered when solar panels are laying down horizontally. Power outage and energy deficit can be addressed efficiently by using knowledge of Global and Diffuse radiation. Assessment of the solar energy system in the form of global and diffuse radiations on the horizontal surface further provides a way to prepare a relatively precise evaluation of the irradiation on sloping surfaces.

Spatial homogeneities are found in the distribution of solar radiation over a large area. Therefore, for a country like India where climate varies from sub-tropical to tropical in the south and temperate to alpine in Himalayan north, it is utmost important to have information about solar radiation to reasonably planned network of solar energy of various regions, so that the distribution of the various components of the solar energy can be effectively approximated and data there on made available for various disciplines of users for better renewable energy utilisation.

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